

Teaching Effectiveness of Secondary School Teachers in Relation to Demographic Factors

DOI : 10.5281/zenodo.8386027

Abstract

The concept of teaching effectiveness revolves around the qualities and characteristics of teacher as a person in the teaching-learning process. The present study aims to study the teaching effectiveness of secondary school teachers in relation to demographic factors such as gender, type of school and experience. For this purpose, 400 secondary school teachers as subjects were selected randomly from secondary schools situated in four districts of Haryana. Teacher Effectiveness Scale (PGTES) developed by Dr. Shallu Puri & Dr. S.C.Gakhar (2010) was used. Findings of the study indicated that male secondary school teachers' teaching was more effective than female teacher's. The present study suggested that it is the responsibility of a teacher to maintain balance between his/her personal and professional life to enhance their teaching effectiveness.

Keywords: Teaching Effectiveness, Secondary School Teachers.

Introduction

Effective teaching is the ability to provide instruction to students with different abilities while incorporating instructional objectives. Teaching effectiveness generally includes teachers' classroom behaviour, teachers' subject knowledge and style of instruction, and teachers' beliefs on pupil learning. Effective Teaching can be extended by teacher's acts in various ways that are favourable to the development of basic skills, understanding, work habits, desirable attitude, value judgement and adequate personal adjustment of the pupils. (Ryans, 1960). Effective teaching should meet three major sets of conditions:

1. The social or cultural group in which the teacher operates involves social values which frequently differ from person to person, community to community, culture to culture and time to time;
2. The grade level and subject matter taught; and
3. Intellectual and personal characteristics of the pupils taught.

An effective teacher is one who promotes positive emotions among students by fostering critical thinking and creativity, showing sensitivity to students' feelings about the subject matter, and promoting an atmosphere of respect. Teacher may run the classroom in an organised, highly structured manner, emphasizing the intellectual content of academic discipline, while another may manage it in a less structured environment, allowing the students much more freedom to choose subject matter and activities that interested them personally. An effective teacher is able to bring about intended learning outcomes, though the nature of learning is still more important (Meera Thakur 2017). Good teachers show a balance of qualities continuous growth for excellence, readiness for guidance; set high value standards so that they can equip the children wisely and effectively. Teacher should have mastery over the subject matter which he teaches; possess communication skills, possess good academic record and have knowledge of the developmental process that takes place in a student. A teacher who has these qualities and exhibits such effective behaviours is likely to exhibit an effective teaching.

In short teaching effectiveness revolves around the qualities and characteristics of teacher as a person in the teaching-learning process.

Review of Literature

Jain (2007) conducted a study on teaching effectiveness of teachers and their attitudes towards teaching profession. The researcher towards teaching professionl researcher compared the teaching

Ranjit Kaur

Assistant Professor,
Deptt.of Education,
Chaudhary Devi Lal University,
Sirsa

Kavita Sharma

Research Scholar,
Deptt.of Education,
Chaudhary Devi Lal University,
Sirsa

Shamshir Singh Dhillon

Assistant Professor,
Deptt.of Education,
Central University of Punjab,
Bathinda

effectiveness of teachers and their attitudes with different demographic factors as sex, type of school and teaching experience. The teaching effectiveness scale was developed by the investigator and attitude scale developed by Goyal which was administrated on 75 teachers of secondary classes of Delhi Schools to collect data. The study revealed the teaching effectiveness and attitudes of teachers towards teaching profession with respect to sex, type of school and teaching. The experienced female teachers teaching in private school exhibited better classroom teaching and negative relationship was found between the attitudes and teaching effectiveness of teachers.

Kulkarni (2000) conducted a comparative study of male and female secondary school teachers with respect to their personality traits, competency, and teaching effectiveness. The sample was randomly selected from 1000 higher secondary school teachers. Data was collected with the help of questionnaire which was analyzed with the help of S.D., percentile and correlation. The findings of the study were:

1) male teachers were more effective than female teachers; 2) there was negative relationship between temperament and teaching effectiveness male and female teachers., 3) there was positive relationship between adjustment and teaching effectiveness of male and female teachers, 4) there was a significant positive relationship between competency and teaching effectiveness of both male and female teachers, 5) there was a significant difference of effective teaching between rural male teachers urban male teachers.

Sharma (2010) conducted a study on teaching effectiveness in relation to academic background, gender and teaching experience among secondary school teachers. The major findings of the study were: 1) teaching effectiveness was significantly related with academic background as gender and teaching experience. 2) there was no significant relationship between academic background and teaching experience with teacher effectiveness of male secondary school teachers, 3) male secondary school teachers with high academic background were more effective in teaching than low academic background.

Singh (1991) studied the Relationships of Teaching Effectiveness with creativity of male and female secondary school teachers of Punjab. Results of this study revealed that teaching effectiveness of male and female teachers was positively related with fluency, flexibility, originality, composite creativity and intelligence.

Justification of the Study

In the present age of cut throat competition students are overburdened to perform efficiently in every sphere of life. Expectations of parents, teachers and society have made them highly confused and stressed. Student's positive interest and attitude in their field can be shaped up to mark only through an effective teacher. Effectiveness may be viewed in the perspective of school climate. So the present study will give an insight into effective teaching which effect teaching effectiveness and revolving around the

qualities and characteristics of teacher as a person ineffective teaching-learning process.

Operational Definition of Term Used

Teaching Effectiveness

Teaching effectiveness is concerned with the relationship between teacher's characteristics, teaching acts and their effects on the educational outcomes of classroom teaching. In this study teaching effectiveness includes teachers' classroom behaviour, teachers' subject knowledge and style of instruction, and teachers' beliefs on pupil learning on the basis of six components.

Objectives of the Study

1. To study the teaching effectiveness of secondary school teachers.
2. To compare the teaching effectiveness of secondary school teachers with respect to gender.
3. To compare the teaching effectiveness of secondary school teachers with respect to school.
4. To compare the teaching effectiveness of secondary school teachers with respect to experience.

Hypotheses

- 1 There is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of secondary school teachers with respect to gender
- 2 There is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of secondary school teachers with respect to type of school.
- 3 There is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of secondary school teachers with respect to experience.

Research methodology

The descriptive survey method was used according to the nature of present study. For the collection of data the researcher surveyed the different secondary schools located in the Haryana for and private secondary school teachers and administered tool to the teachers. The 400 secondary school teachers were selected through multistage probability sampling technique. A Teacher Effectiveness Scale (PGTES) developed by Dr. Shallu Puri & Dr. S.C. Gakhar (2010) was used. The descriptive statistics such as mean and standard deviation was used. Inferential statistics such as t-test was also employed for comparing teaching effectiveness.

Delimitation of the Study

The present study was confined to:

1. The state of Haryana only.
2. Four districts of state of Haryana.
3. Sample of 400 secondary school teachers only.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data

Table No. 1

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Male and Female Secondary School Teachers

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Male	2.59	203	55.66	2.97
Female	2.53	203	54.02	

From the above table it can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness among male

and female of secondary school teachers are 2.59 and 2.53 with respect to SD= 55.66 and 54.02. In the table the t-value is 2.97 which is above than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of male and female secondary school teachers' is rejected and this is because female teachers have dual role to play.

Table No.2

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Male and Female Secondary School Teachers Having 0-5 Teaching Experience

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Male	2.29	53	46.89	4.55
Female	2.57	53	54.50	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness of male and female secondary school teachers having 0-5 years teaching experience are 2.29 and 2.57 with respect to SD= 46.89 and 54.50. In the table the t value is 4.55 which is above than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of male and female secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience' is rejected.

Table No.3

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Male and Female Secondary School Teachers Having 5-10 Teaching Experience

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Male	2.57	67	56.14	.71
Female	2.54	67	55.91	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness of male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 years teaching experience are 2.57 and 2.54 with respect to SD= 56.14 and 55.91. In the table the t-value is .71 which is less than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is not significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience' is accepted.

Table No. 4

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Male and Female Secondary School Teachers Having Above 10 Years Teaching Experience

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Male	2.73	66	51.24	3.49
Female	2.60	66	50.59	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness of male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience are 2.73 and 2.60 with respect to SD= 51.24 and 50.59. In the table the t-value is above than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience' is rejected. This result

was also in tune with the findings of Liegh (2007) who also discussed about the experience as it had strongest effect on effective teaching.

Table No.5

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Government and Private Secondary School Teachers

Type of School	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-Value
Government	2.51	202	55.29	2.93
Private	2.62	202	53.59	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness of government and private secondary school teachers are 2.51 and 2.62 with respect to SD= 55.29. In the table the t-value is 2.93 which is above than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government and private secondary school teachers' is rejected. It is because government schools have lack of infrastructure and inadequate number of teachers. It is also followed by Mittal, Jai Parkash (1989).

Table No.6

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Government and Private Secondary School Teachers Having 0-5 Teaching Experience

Type of School	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Government	2.37	34	48.99	.63
Private	2.35	34	53.19	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness of government and private secondary school teachers having 0-5 years teaching experience are 2.37 and 2.35 with respect to SD= 48.99 and 53.19. In the table the t-value is .63 which is less than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is not significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government and private secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience' is accepted.

Table No.7

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Government and Private Secondary School Teachers Having 5-10 Teaching Experience

Type of School	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Government	2.56	33	53.69	3.50
Private	2.43	33	58.21	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness of government and private secondary school teachers having 5-10 years teaching experience are 2.56 and 2.43 with respect to SD= 53.69 and 58.21. In the table the t value is 3.50 which is above than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government and private secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience' is rejecte

Table No.8

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Government and Private Secondary School Teachers Having Above 10 Years Teaching Experience

Type of School	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Government	93.28	66	21.54	1.02
Private	94.68	66	21.59	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness among government and private secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience are 93.28 and 94.68 with respect to SD= 21.54 and 21.59. in the table the t-value is 1.02 which is less than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is not significant at 0,05 level. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government and private Secondary school teachers having above 10 teaching experience' is accepted (Rao 2011).

Table No.9

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Government Male and Female Secondary School Teachers

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Government Male	2.56	101	54.22	3.40
Government Female	2.46	101	56.16	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness of government male and female secondary school teachers are 2.56 and 2.43 with respect to SD= 54.22 and 56.16. in the table the t-value is 3.40 which is above than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government male and female male and female secondary school teachers' is rejected. This is because; male teachers have more opportunities for in-service training to make their teaching effective.

Table No.10

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Government Male and Female Secondary School Teachers Having 0-5 Teaching Experience

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Government Male	2.37	34	48.99	.635
Government Female	2.35	34	53.19	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness of government male and female secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience are 2.37 and 2.35 with respect to SD= 48.99 and 53.19. In the table the t-value is .635 which is less than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is not significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government male and female secondary school teachers' is accepted.

Table No.11

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Government Male and Female Secondary School Teachers Having 5-10 Teaching Experience

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Government Male	2.56	33	53.69	3.50
Government Female	2.43	33	58.21	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness of government male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience are 2.56 and 2.43 with respect to SD= 53.69 and 58.21. In the table the t-value is 3.50 which is above than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience' is rejected.

Table No.12

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Government Male and Female Secondary School Teachers Having Above 10 Years Teaching Experience

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Government Male	2.77	33	52.07	4.20
Government Female	2.61	33	54.99	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness of government male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience are 2.77 and 2.61 with respect to SD= 57.07 and 54.99. In the table the t-value is 4.20 which are above than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience' is rejected. This finding is supported by Sundararajan and Srinivasan (1992).

Table No.13

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Private Male and Female Secondary School Teachers

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	T-Value
Private Male	2.62	102	57.12	.887
Private Female	2.60	102	51.16	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness of private male and female secondary school teachers are 2.62 and 2.60 with respect to SD= 57.12 and 51.16. In the table the t-value is .887 which is less than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is not significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of private male and female secondary school teachers' is accepted.

Table No.14

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Private Male and Female Secondary School Teachers Having 0-5 Teaching Experience

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Private Male	2.61	35	60.86	1.50
Private Female	2.56	35	54.42	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness of private male and female secondary school teachers having 0-5 teaching experience are 2.61 and 2.56 with respect to SD=60.86 and 54.42. In the table the t-value is 1.50 which is less than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is not significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of private male and female secondary school teachers' is accepted.

Table No.15

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Private Male and Female Secondary School Teachers Having 5-10 Teaching Experience

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Private Male	2.58	34	58.92	1.69
Private Female	2.64	34	52.32	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness of private male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 teaching experience are 2.58 and 2.64 with respect to SD=58.92 and 52.32. In the table the t-value is 1.69 which is less than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is not significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of private male and female secondary school teachers' is accepted.

Table No.16

Significance of Difference between Teaching Effectiveness of Private Male and Female Secondary School Teachers Having Above 10 Years Teaching Experience

Gender	Mean	N	Std. Deviation	t-value
Private Male	2.69	33	50.89	2.59
Private Female	2.59	33	47.45	

It can be observed that mean score of teaching effectiveness of private male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience are 2.69 and 2.59 with respect to standard deviations 58.89 and 47.45. In the table the t-value is 2.59 which are above than tabulated value 1.98. Hence it is significant at 0.05 levels. Thus the hypothesis i.e. 'there is no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of private male and female secondary school teachers' is rejected. It is because in private field male teachers have more effective student teacher interaction and informal academic support than female teachers which make their teaching comparatively effective.

Findings

1. It was found that there was significant difference between teaching effectiveness of male and female secondary school teachers and teaching effectiveness of male secondary school teachers is higher than female secondary school teachers because female teachers have dual role to play and it is possible that resultant stress created would effects their level of teaching effectiveness.
2. It was found that there was significant difference between teaching effectiveness of male and female secondary school teachers having 0-5 years teaching experience and teaching effectiveness of female secondary school teachers is higher than male secondary school teachers.
3. It was found that there was significant difference between teaching effectiveness of male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 years teaching experience and teaching effectiveness of male secondary school teachers is higher than female secondary school teachers.
4. It was found that there was significant difference between teaching effectiveness of male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience and teaching effectiveness of male secondary school teachers is higher than female secondary school teachers.
5. It was found that there was significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government and private secondary school teachers and teaching effectiveness of private secondary school teachers is higher than government Secondary school teachers because government schools have lack of infrastructure and inadequate number of teachers.
6. It was found that there was no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government and private secondary school teachers having 0-5 years teaching experience and teaching effectiveness of private and government secondary school teachers is almost equal.
7. It was found that there was significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government and private secondary school teachers having 5-10 years teaching experience and teaching effectiveness of government secondary school teachers is higher than private Secondary school teachers.
8. It was found that there was significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government and private secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience and teaching effectiveness of government secondary school teachers is higher than private Secondary school teachers as private schools teachers are more effective in respect to their subject mastery, presentation style, motivational strategies and effective communication and during 5-10 and above 10 years teaching experience government and private teachers were equally effective.
9. It was found that there was significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government

male and female secondary school teachers and teaching effectiveness of government male secondary school teachers is higher than govt. female Secondary school teachers because male teachers have more opportunities for in-service training to make their teaching effective.

10. It was found that there was no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government male and female secondary school teachers having 0-5years teaching experience and teaching effectiveness of govt. male and female secondary school teachers is almost same.
11. It was found that there was significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 years teaching experience and teaching effectiveness of govt. male secondary school teachers is higher than govt. female Secondary school teachers.
12. It was found that there was significant difference between teaching effectiveness of government male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience and teaching effectiveness of govt. male secondary school teachers is higher than government female Secondary school teachers because male teachers more independent, have higher social economic status, are more efficient in taking work related decisions and achieving goals such as promotions, pay, status and so on.
13. It was found that there was no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of private male and female secondary school teachers and teaching effectiveness of private male and private female Secondary school teachers is almost equal.
14. It was found that there was no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of private male and female secondary school teachers having 0-5years teaching experience and teaching effectiveness of private male secondary school teachers is higher than female secondary school teachers.
15. It was found that there was no significant difference between teaching effectiveness of private male and female secondary school teachers having 5-10 years teaching experience and teaching effectiveness of private male secondary school teachers is higher than female secondary school teachers.
16. It was found that there was significant difference between teaching effectiveness of private male and female secondary school teachers having above 10 years teaching experience and teaching effectiveness of private male secondary school teachers is higher than female secondary school teachers as in private field male teachers have more effective student teacher interaction and informal academic support which make their teaching comparatively effective.

Conclusion

On the basis of above findings it was found that that male secondary school teachers' teaching is

more effective than female secondary school teachers because female teachers have undue pressure to keep the balance between the family & job and it is possible that resultant stress created would effects their level of teaching effectiveness.

Suggestions for Further Studies

1. The present study was limited to state of Haryana only which can be conducted in other states also.
2. The present study was conducted on secondary school teachers as the same can be conducted on different population such as primary, middle and university level teachers
3. The present study was limited to 400 secondary school teachers only which can be further conducted with a large sample.
4. Similar study can be conducted on other variables such as teacher efficacy, job stress and job satisfaction etc.

References

1. Ding, C., & Sherman, H. (2006). *Teaching effectiveness and student achievement: Examining the relationship. Educational research quarterly, 29 (4), 40-51.*
2. Edwin, S.A. (1991). *The perception of principals on teaching effectiveness and the midcareer teacher. Dissertation abstracts international: section A. humanities and social sciences, 52(5), 1589.*
3. Himani, A., Shailendra, P., & Goutami, S. (2012). *Teacher effectiveness as related to enthusiastic and non enthusiastic trait. Educational quest, 3(2), 117-121.*
4. J. Mittal (1989). *An exploratory study of teachers' motivation to work and its relationship with school climate of schools, M.Phil., Edu. Jamia Millia*
5. Jain, R. (2007). *A study of teaching effectiveness of teachers and their attitudes towards teaching profession. Journal of Indian Education, 33(1), 77-89.*
6. Jayaramanna, K. (2001). *A study of teacher effectiveness in relation to work orientation and achievement of students at primary level. Andhra University, India.*
7. Kulkarni, A.H. (2000). *A comparative study of male and female secondary school teachers with respect to their personality traits, competency and teacher effectiveness, Shivaji university, India.*
8. Kumar, A. (2013). *A study of professional commitment in relation to thinking style, job values and teacher's effectiveness of teachers working in teacher training institutions of Haryana. Maharshi Dayanand University, Rohtak, India. Retrieved June 01, 2013 from <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/7923>.*
9. Leigh (2007). *Measuring teacher effectiveness. Blog Archive, 2007, May 20.*
10. Marsland, Eric (2000). *An examination of the role of the multiple intelligence in studies of effective teaching. Dissertation abstracts international: Section A. Humanities and Social Sciences, 39(3), June 2001, 639.*
11. Moshahid, Mohd (2017). *A study of adjustment among government and private secondary school*

- teachers, An Int. J. of Education Applied social sciences, vol.no. 8 (1), pp- 157-162.*
12. Puri, Shallu and Gakhar S.C. (2010). *Teacher Effectiveness Scale, department of Education, Panjab University, Chandigarh- 160 014.*
 13. Rao, N. (2011). *Astudy of teacher effectiveness in relation to their value domain. Innovations in Teacher Education, 2(2), July, 2011, 31-34.*
 14. Ryans (1960), *characteristics of teachers: Their Descriptions, and Appraisals, Wasshington, D.C.: American council on Education.*
 15. S.Srinivasan (1992). *Personality traits of primary school teachers and their attitude towards teaching, M. Phill. In education, Annanmalai University, Tamil Naidu.*
 16. Sharma (2010). *A study of teaching effectiveness in relation to the academic background, gender and teaching experience among secondary school teachers, (M.Ed dissertation, Education), Aligarh Muslim University, India.*
 17. Thakur, Meera (2017). *Teacher Effectiveness as related to cognitive style and emotional competence, department of education, Himachal Pradesh University.*
 18. Verma, Suminder (2016). *Teacher Educators' effectiveness in relation to Job Satisfaction, Well Being and Institutional climate, department of education, Himachal Pradesh University.*